

at a uniform rate of 12.5 t/ha at 50 d of growth (N was 1.1% of fresh biomass). Excess was removed from the field. GM sown simultaneously in an adjacent field was cut, transported, and incorporated in the other treatment.

Short-duration (105 d) rice variety ADT36 was planted 1, 7, and 15 d after

GM incorporation. We planted at different days after submergence in the no-GM plot.

P and potash were basally applied to all plots; N was applied at varied rates and split as 50% basal, 25% active tillering, and 25% panicle initiation stages. Grain yield was recorded at 14% moisture; straw was sun-dried.

GM significantly increased rice grain and straw yields (see table). GM transported and incorporated gave the highest yield. Time interval after incorporation showed no significant variation in yield. This indicates the possibility of planting rice the day after GM incorporation. N at 100 kg/ha gave the highest yield. □

Crop management

Managing rice ratoons

S. Sahoo and D. Lenka, Agronomy Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, India

Beushaning is the practice of plowing young rice crops in 5–10 cm of standing water followed by laddering, redistributing seedlings to fill gaps, and hand weeding. Beushaning loosens and aerates the soil, enhances tillering and root growth, and improves drought and pest tolerance. We conducted field research to determine whether beushaning also improves ratoon rice yield.

CR1009 was grown during 1989 monsoon (Jul–Dec) and ratooned during 1989–90 summer (Dec–Apr). It was transplanted and fertilized with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. We harvested after 166 d and left 10- or 20-cm stubble. The ratoon was fertilized at 20-4.3-8.3, 40-8.7-16.7, or 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Half of the ratoon crop was beushaned.

Combinations of these treatments (2 × 3 × 2) were imposed on the ratoon crop laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Sarathi (119 d) was transplanted during summer for comparison.

Application of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the ratoon crop significantly increased panicles/m², grains/panicle, and grain weight (Table 1).

Beushaning had no significant effect on any of the yield-contributing characters. Though it increased the tillering ability of the stubble, it decreased hills/m².

Ratoons from 10-cm-high stubble yielded 2 t/ha, 0.54 t more than the yield of ratoons from 20-cm-high stubble.

Table 1. Yield and yield characters of ratoon crops.^a

	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Chaffy grains (no./panicle)	1,000- grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	
					Grain	Straw
Fertility level (kg/ha)						
N						
P						
K						
20	4.3	8.3	299	67	16.0	21.8
40	8.7	16.7	281	70	15.7	22.3
60	13	25	389	77	14.3	23.7
LSD (0.05)			49	2	ns	0.8
ns						
Stubble height (cm)						
10			333	74	14.0	22.4
20			313	69	16.6	22.8
LSD (0.05)			ns	2	2.5	ns
ns						
Cultural practice						
No beushaning			332	72	15.5	22.5
Beushaning			314	71	15.1	22.7
Mean			323	72	15.3	22.6
ns						

^ans = not significant.

Straw yield was also greater for the 10-cm stubble.

The ratoon crop yielded approximately half as much as the main crop. Ratoon crop duration was 47 d less than that of the main crop (Table 2).

The summer crop Sarathi yield was higher than that of the ratoon. Cultivation

cost was \$142/ha for the ratoon crop and \$209/ha for the summer crop. Net profit was \$15/ha more for the summer crop. Ratooning should not be practiced unless problems such as waterlogging or time constraints confront farmers. □

Table 2. Comparison of main and ratoon crops.

Character	Main crop Sarathi	Ratoon crop CR1009
Plant height (cm)	77.6	47.1
Hills (no./m ²)	49.6	44.9
Tillers (no./m ²)	270	451
Tillers (no./hill)	5.4	9.9
Panicles (no./m ²)	244	323
Panicles affected by stem borer (no./m ²)	20.6	14.2
Grains (no./panicle)	124	72
Chaffy grains (no./panicle)	22	15
Panicle length (cm)	22.2	16.7
1,000-grain weight (g)	24.3	22.6
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.2	1.8
Straw yield (t/ha)	4.9	2.5
Chaffy grain yield (t/ha)	0.3	0.1
Duration (d)	166	119
Grains (kg/ha per d)	19.5	14.7

Effect of plant growth enhancer on lowland rice yield

P. S. Ongkingco and F. D. Garcia, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

We studied the effect of WOKOZIM, a growth enhancer extracted from seaweed, on lowland rice yield in 1989 wet season (WS) and 1990 dry season (DS) at irrigated sites in Maligaya and in Midsayap, North Cotabato.

Trials were laid out in randomized complete block design with four replications. Wetbed seedlings were transplanted 21 d after sowing. Treatments were the recommended fertilizer rate (60-30-30 kg NPK/ha in WS and 90-30-